

MOIN4Herbie deliverable 1 - Requirements specification workshop with sensor platform operators and technicians

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Figure 1: MOIN4Herbie logo

Purpose of this document

This document contains deliverable #1 *Requirements specification workshop with sensor platform operators and technicians* of the project MOIN4Herbie - Maintenance Ontology and audit log Integration for Herbie funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable #1 is part of work package 2 Maintenance metadata requirements specifications and development of generalized protocols.

Requirements specification workshop with sensor platform operators and technicians

Introduction

In the requirements specification workshop, the project is introduced to involved platform operators, technicians and scientists. Furthermore, the requirements

workshop aims to gather input from the involved parties on how to set up Herbie so that it can be used in practice. In MOIN4Herbie, the focus is on two use cases: Boknis Eck underwater observatory and Tesperhude station. Both use cases are introduced to all project participants and practical limitations in the field are discussed.

In order to focus on each use case, two workshops were carried out in June 2024, for Boknis Eck at GEOMAR in Kiel and for Tesperhude at Hereon in Geesthacht.

Agenda

The agenda was identical for both workshops:

- Introduction of MOIN4Herbie
- Introduction of Herbie
- General overview of specific use case (Boknis Eck or Tesperhude)
- Introduction of current maintenance and equipment metadata / data handling at use case
- Planning maintenance and notifications module: Past experience and requirements
- Offline capabilities: What functionalities are necessary?
- Equipment module: Requirements, how is equipment and maintenance metadata managed currently?
- Summary and discussion

Results of workshop Tesperhude

Introduction of MOIN4Herbie

Project Overview: Maintenance Ontology and Audit Log Integration for Herbie This project, funded as a two-year initiative under the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), started in April 2024. It is a collaborative effort involving the Helmholtz Coastal Data Center (HCDC), Herbie developers from the Hereon Institute of Metallic Biomaterials, and GEOMAR's data management team.

Objectives The project aims to achieve several key objectives:

1. **On-site Digitalization:** Implement a web-based system for recording sensor maintenance information, aligned with existing ontologies.
2. **Ontology Guided User Support:** Enhance interoperability and traceability through improved usability and accessibility.
3. **Linking Metadata Records:** Connect metadata records to near-real-time data streams.
4. **Standardized API Integration:** Incorporate and contribute to the OGC SensorThingsAPI, as implemented by the HMC project STAMPLATE.

Approach The project approach focuses on several key areas:

- a. **Digitalization:** Utilize a browser-based system for metadata recording.
- b. **Use Cases:** Implement and test the system at Boknis Eck and Tesperhude.
- c. **ELN Herbie Expansion:** Enhance Herbie with sensor maintenance functionalities, building on the HMC project MetaCook. This includes:
 - i. Evaluating and specifying appropriate ontologies and protocols.
 - ii. Developing modules for planning maintenance and notifications.
 - iii. Creating offline capabilities.
 - iv. Expanding the equipment module.
- d. **Integration:** Ensure maintenance metadata integrates seamlessly with other software and data streams.

Introduction of Herbie

Herbie is an electronic lab book designed for storing the (meta)data of materials. It addresses various challenges. A major challenge is the lack of semantic standardization across research fields, resulting in various file formats and inconsistent annotations. To overcome this, Herbie utilizes ontologies and semantic annotations to create structured input forms.

This approach offers several advantages: enhanced understanding, prevention of data loss due to personnel changes, and improved flexibility, allowing easy adaptation to new research areas. Herbie is particularly suited for maintaining documentation.

Currently, Herbie employs several semantic ontologies. The developers collaborate with institutes such as KIT, FZJ, DLR, and others.

General Overview of Tesperhude Station

At Tesperhude Station, a ferrybox equipped with multiple sensors transmits data from 21 sensors via HELMI, while additional sensors are maintained by Hereon technical personnel. Currently, sensors are calibrated twice a year.

However, there is a lack of serial number and other sensor description information being transferred and stored digitally. This data shall be added to the sensor registry (<https://registry.o2a-data.de/items>). An open task is determining which data should go to the sensor registry versus Herbie, and how to establish communication protocols between the two systems in case that sensor data changes.

Introduction of Current Maintenance and Equipment Metadata / Data Handling

By Hereon personnel, a prototype of an internal maintenance app for sensor maintenance data is presented, highlighting that much of the metadata for

Hereon's sensors is stored in Excel files, though some are in the AWI REGISTRY. The O2A registry (<https://registry.o2a-data.de/items>) assigns UUIDs to items, which can also be found in the downloaded JSON for each item. There is a need to distinguish between data from the sensor registry and Moin4Herbie. A Hereon technician presented an Access database used for electronic metadata storage, which requires manual input but will aid in adapting Herbie.

Equipment Module: Requirements and Current Management

A basic data flow diagram was created based on user input.

Figure 2: Basic flow diagram for sensor maintenance data developed during Tesperhude requirements workshop.

The lab book requirements include having to provide information only once and integrating it everywhere else necessary, and a subscription option for platform-specific maintenance reports. The maintenance lab book aims to track the lifecycle of each sensor, including its location, maintenance timestamps, and UUID from the O2A registry. Not all information in Herbie will be pushed to the registry, but links to MOIN4Herbie can be added. Herbie serves as the primary source of truth. For sensor locations, it is essential to know the exact placement on the platform, which is particularly important for Boknis Eck divers. A graphic of the platform with sensor locations, maintenance records, and the ability to add new fields (though not in-field) are also necessary.

For the platform section, free text fields for miscellaneous information, an overview graphic, and details about ferryboxes (flow, valves, control unit) are required. Additionally, a general overview of current equipment deployment and platform status (e.g., electricity outages) should be provided.

Planning Maintenance and Notifications Module: Past Experiences and Requirements

Maintenance alerts should be sent via a chat software to interested parties, along with email reminders. Emails should include to-do lists for upcoming maintenance, defined intervals, and configurable settings for reminder timing and recipients. Plugins for Teams or GitLab, in addition to emails, would be beneficial.

Offline Capabilities: Necessary Functionalities

The current application of Herbie cannot yet work offline, but this capability is planned for MOIN4Herbie. Photo uploads are already possible. Synchronization is a challenge for offline capability, with a proposed solution of checking out parts of the app for field maintenance updates. Simultaneous work on the same section by multiple offline devices will not be possible.

Summary and Discussion

A new scientist at Hereon will be able test the ELN. After the second requirements workshop for Boknis Eck, decisions will be made regarding which ontologies to use. Following this, a cycle of short update meetings will begin to ensure the development stays on track.

Results of workshop Boknis Eck

The presentation of the project and Herbie were repeated at this workshop. See the Tesperhude workshsop for details.

General Overview of Boknis Eck

Boknis Eck is a time series station that has been operational since 1957, conducting monthly series of measurements. These measurements are typically taken one day before trips to the underwater node. Data collected includes parameters such as CTD (Conductivity, Temperature, Depth) and Secchi depth, among others. More detailed information can be found at Boknis Eck Facilities.

Boknis Eck Underwater Node The underwater node expedition occurs the day after the time series station measurements. It will restart once the new Boknis Eck station is redeployed. This is planned for later in 2024.

During these trips, the scientists on the ship collect calibration samples and other data at various depths. Divers operate independently from the scientists.

The setup of the underwater node includes a land station at a nearby campsite, a data and power cable, an underwater distributor, the underwater node (currently missing), and a tower with additional attached sensors.

Research Diver Report Divers at Boknis Eck primarily perform cleaning tasks and replace sensors when necessary. They deploy from an inflatable boat and have a live video transmission from the seabed, though it cannot be saved. Communication with divers is sometimes possible. Divers also use cameras to take photos or videos. Dive documentation is handwritten and lacks scientific information, with observations on vegetation communicated verbally to GEOMAR colleagues.

Requirements for Boknis Eck

Technology Perspective A GEOMAR technician presented a “seatable” solution: an online-based, GDPR-compliant no-code database with advanced table editing features. This solution includes the Boknis Eck inventory, which has been continuously expanded since the second half of 2023. The inventory information and relationships are detailed and complete.

Practically, Boknis Eck comprises a logical node with four physical measurement platforms that continuously collect and provide data. Regular trips with the Littorina are conducted to take measurements and samples at different depths using CTD and water ring scoop, among other methods.

Science Perspective The integration of Littorina trip data with Boknis Eck sensor calibration results is crucial. It is important to maintain transparent separation of tasks and information content between OSIS, the GEOMAR Ocean Science Information System, and MOIN4Herbie.

Summary and discussion

The requirements workshops are a first step to defining the necessities of Herbie to be used in a sensor maintenance setting. Its results will be used when evaluating the existing ontologies for usage within the MOIN4Herbie context (deliverable 3).

During the workshops, a good understanding of what both use cases entail and what is planned in MOIN4Herbie was exchanged between the participants. Future close collaboration within the project is desired.

Figure 3: Participants of Boknis Eck requirements workshop in front of ship Littorina